

Syrien Arabe Republic

Damascus

Story of the oldest city in the world

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1- Introduction

Syría is that portion of the Middle East bordered on the west by the Mediterranean, separated from the Anatolian plateau by Taurus Mountains

and from Mesopotamia by the Euphrates, and which extends southward into Arabian Peninsula. Its position on the world map at the juncture of three continents of Europe, Asia, Africa, its place on the great incense and silk trade routes linking India and the Mediterranean by way of the Arabic Gulf and the Red sea for a history of such breadth and richness that European history pales by comparison into a poor relation in some distant backwater.

In the heart of what is a magnificent region, there emerges from the barren and glinting stone. A city synonymous with the land (in Arabic both bear the name Sham): Damascus protected from the western rains by the lofty ranges of Lebanon and Anti-Lebanon, sheltered from the chill gales of the north by Qalamun and from the southern winds by the Druze Jabal

The Barada winds through a narrow gorge and emerges close to the village of Rabweh in the Damascus floodplain before flowing further twenty-two miles and finally emptying into lake Umayyad to the east. In addition to the water from a multitude of little springs and wadis running down the mountainside, thirteen miles from the city the source Ayn Al-Fija.

Fig(2) Barada river - the source Ayn Al – Fija.

Damascus

2. Damascus city

The city of Damascus occurs on the borders of the desert at the upstream of the hollow plains of Syria, the Galilee valleys and the Mediterranean coast, in the middle of a fertile oasis, (Ghouta), that surrounds it from three sides. It is bordered to the west by the 1150 meter high Kasuon Mountain, whereas the city itself is 700 meters above the sea level. It benefits from the inflow of seven effluents of Barada River. People contemporaneous to Saint John of Damascus surnamed him after the river for his abundant knowledge and sublime virtues.

2.1 The city during the Canaanite and Amorite periods

The existence of Damascus prior to the Aramaean era is a proven fact based on the pharaonic documents that were discovered in Amarna, and the archeological excavations that were conducted in the Umayyad Mosque courtyard in 1965. The city Wall in that period was built of large stones measuring between 80*60 to 100*60 cm, two meters thick, and from 5-6 meters high, supported by bars, with an average of one cylindrical bar per 4 meters length, with bars built in stones .

2.2 Aramaean period (1100 BC -732 BC)

The city was first conceived as an urban center on a hill at the heart of the ancient city. But Aramaeans never went beyond this limit, which has been established from the excavations that were conducted near the Roman sites. In layers, no trace was found of any settlement previous to the Romans, which suggests that the Aramaean city did not extend beyond that, and that its wall remained unchanged during subsequent periods

Fig (3) The City and the Wall during Aramaic period (1100 BC -732 BC)

2.3 The Greek period

After the conquest of the East by Alexander the Great and his invasion of Persian territories, Damascus fell under Greek rule. Greeks even inhabited their distinct parts areas, constituting thus a new city, juxtaposed to the Aramaean one, following the model of Greek cities in urbanization and structure, with the typical straight streets and perpendicular streets on the eastern part of the ancient city. As they are accustomed to, Greeks settled in the eastern side of the Wall, with streets running in chess board style, and consequently, the Wall was extended to circumscribe those new areas

2.4 The Roman period

This period starts from 64 BC, and the city was part of the Decapolis, where the Romans inhabited the fourth Damascus hill, and built a gated Wall around the city. In terms of urbanization, Damascus embodied the Greco-Roman rectangular shape (1550x850 m), all along Barada River and on its south bank. The Wall and the gates surrounded the architectural components, the streets, the temple, the buildings that have a general vocation, and the residential areas. It was during this period that the Wall started to take its shape,

Fig(4) Damascus in the Roman Period

Fig (5) Jupiter Temple During Roman Period

2.5 The Byzantine period

The year 395 A.D. came, and no urban features were added to the city but the construction of some churches. And as a result of the city's decadence on the military, financial and demographic levels due to a multitude of factors, the transformations that were introduced to Damascus rampart and its components only concerned some architectural aspects that entered in the constitution of gates, besides some changes in the bulk of the wall itself.

Fig (6) Christian basilica – St . johon Baptist (Yahya)

Fig (7) House of Saint Ananias – Damascus

2.6 The Umayyad period

In the year 41 of Hegira/661 AD., Muawiya wanted to establish the capital city of the Umayyad Caliphate, so he made of Damascus the capital of the State..

As a matter of fact, one of the marvelous novelties that ancient Damascus witnessed during that era was the construction of the Umayyad Mosque under Al-Waleed Ibn Abd al-Malik, which shifted the center from the street called straight to the area surrounding the Umayyad Mosque, and all improvement and construction works focused on this zone. But neither the wall nor its gates were the subjects of any substantial works.

Fig (8) Plan- Section – Umayyad Mosque 705AD

Fig (9) AlNeser Dome – Umayyad Mosque

Fig(10) Al- Sahen (court) Umayyad Mosque

Fig(11) Menarets (Qaitbay – Arus – Isa)

2.7 The Seljuq-Ayyubid period

Nur ad-Dine Zengi of Aleppo was able to dominate Damascus in 549 H/1154 A.D...(31). Nur ad-Dine's rule inaugurated a new area of prosperity and power for the city, which imparted her a momentum of extensive progress and economic development, due to the security and stability it enjoyed. During this era, a new Wall was built with smaller gates, which was normal, given the expertise Nur ad Dine had acquired in Aleppo.

New minarets were added on top of gates, and even the second Tower called 'AL-NURE' was discovered in the excavations to the south of Damascus, at the airport node, which led to the identification and delimitation of the wall that was built in this era. In the Ayyubid period, fortifications of the Wall were resumed, focusing on building towers and restoration of Damascus citadel. The Ayyubid period in general, and Nur ad Dine's rule in particular, were characterized by a special defensive and architectural pattern, besides a reuse of old and previously carved out stones, to meet the requirements of fast execution of works, .

Fig(12) Al-Bimaristan AlNouri 1154Ad

Fig(13) Al Madrassa AlNouria 1167AD– Hammam Nour Al din 1169AD

Fig(12) Citadel – plan Uyyupid period 1176Ad

Fig(13) Citadel – East Elevation Uyyupid period

Fig(14) Citadel – photo from north side of the wall

Fig(15) Al Madrasah Al Shamiya –the sister –to Salh Al dien /1191AD/

2.8 The Mamluk period

In 1260, Damascus became one of the most important Mamlukite Wilayats of the Levant, and gained back its prosperity, especially under Baibars. Due to wars waged in that era, much damage was inflicted upon it, mainly on the southern rampart. Since then, the importance of the Damascus rampart started to witness a regression from the military and civilian aspects.

Fig (16) Muqarnas in the Mamluk period

Fig (17) Hammam Al Tawrizi 1419 AD

2.9 The Ottoman Period 1516 A.D.

During the Ottoman period, the Wall became abandoned, since it lost its role as an efficient defensive wall of the city. Consequently, it suffered from neglect and deterioration. Starting from 1830, Ibrahim Pasha took on the demolition of huge parts of the wall, and rebuilt them in other areas. This demolition process was maintained for quite a period of time. It is noticed also that Damascus witnessed an expansion of mainly its local market places, which by the end of the Ottoman period required the filling up of long segments of the trench around the wall and the citadel.[3]

Fig (18) Almadras Al sulimania1566Ad – Masjed Fathy 1742 Ad Ottman Period

**Fig (19) Al azem Place 1749Ad – Maktab Annber 1886Ad – Takia As-Sulimania1559-1566 Ad
Ottoman Period**

2.10 The end of the Ottoman Empire and pangs of Westernization

The last sixty years of Ottoman Rule are known as the Tanzimat Period'. It was a time of administrative reform and modernization and a new emphasis on city planning and development evolved due in part to the increased prosperity from European trade. "During these 50 years [1860-1910] the city was transformed at a rate not experienced since Nural-Din's time"

The new urbanism that developed during Tanzimat was based on 3 principles, set

- 1- New Laws and Regulations Concerning Damascus; especially, the Ottoman Building System (August 1897), amended on April 4. 1910.
- 2- Projects of Developing the Old City Within The Wall.
- 3- Project of Providing Water and Covering the canals.
- 4- Projects of Transport
- 5- Projects of Electricity, Telegraph
- 6- Project of Utilities Buildings

Concentration will be placed on the effects of these projects which are still connected with the tissue of the city of Damascus.

FERNANDO DE ARANDA
UN ARQUITECTO
ESPAÑOL EN SIRIA

F. Aranda

Fig (20) Al Hejaz station – al Abed building 1910-De Aranda

Fig (21) Tinkez Mousque – Michal Ecochard 1935

Fig (22) Arch. Abd –Al Razzaq Malass – Al Barلمان 1928 Ad - Qaser Al adel 1948 1952 -- Ayn Al – Figa. 1931 Ad

Fig (23) Kalil Al- Fraa - Faculty of civil engineering 1961 Ad – the national Bank 1956 Ad

Fig (24) | Damascus land used - 1936

3-Urban developments – Damascus

Damascus is a large geographical region, containing mountain ranges, green plains, known as Ghouta and barren land leading to the desert. It is considered as a rich oasis with moderate climate, penetrated by a great river, called Barada.

This region is the third region in the Levant (Bilad Al Sham), which observed the oldest human settlement in the Modern Stone Age that dates back at least to the Neanderthal era. This fact is proved by the archaeological discoveries in caves of Yabroud, Al Qalamoun mountains, Qassyoun, Al Mazzeh and others.

In the 9th and 8th millennium BC (Neolith era), the first forms of urban structure and planning, the social and economical impacts appeared by changing the house projection from circle to square or rectangular. Since that era, the harmony and interaction between man and his environment appeared in the use of traditional construction materials (stone, mud and wood) for the public and private architecture, as this region was very rich in these materials, which helped to enhance the human life in the region. Since then until this day, life did not stop in the Damascus region, and excavation almost any where revealed evidences of human existence in this region.

With the beginning of the western interference in the internal Arab affairs, Damascus started to lose its economic importance, where many handicrafts exterminated. French occupation for Syria lasted from 1920 till 1946, when Syria gained independency as the first Arab country to be free from the foreign occupation.

After independency Syria was unstable because of many military coups and from 1958 - 1963 Damascus witnessed remarkable urban development, and after the 8th March revolution in 1963 Damascus witnessed development in laws and regulations for the benefit of labors and farmers. The war of 1967 had a great impact on Damascus due to the large number of emigrants from Golan Heights, which was occupied by Israel in 1967. During the period President Hafez Al Assad, 1970 - 2000, there was a remarkable development, where new quarters and projects were established (service, water and electricity).

Through out its history, Damascus witnessed several earthquakes, the biggest of which was in 1759. This earthquake caused a great damage to the residential and historical urban structure, such as the Umayyad mosque, the citadel and Asa`ad Pacha Khan. Before that, Damascus tolerated strong earthquakes in the 12th century and to almost total destruction the Mongolian Timor Lank in the beginning of the 5th century.

In 1860 the quarter of Bab Touma was destroyed and burned during the sectarian disorders, and during the 1925 revolution, the French army destroyed

the residential quarter in Damascus, such as Al Midan, Al Shaghour and Sidi Meqdad, which was re-planed as Al Hariqa quarter.

Damascus is historically a compound city, that the historical eras are represented in its urban structure and there exists an architectural evidence for each period and era. The main characteristic of Damascus urban structure is that it is an environmental urban structure reflecting the relationship between man and his environment. Damascus was food and industry self sufficient through the interrelation between the urban city and the agricultural countryside, in addition to desert (pastures), and it used to produce all its needs with exporting them, but Damascus lost this advantage after middle of the 9th century, when it was invade by the European products.

4-Cultural Structure of the Damascus City

The Damascus region, like other regions in the Levant (Bilad Al Sham), had cultural and religious unit since the Neolith age. Archaeological evidences, especially architecture, show that Arab people that inhabited this region had one (unified) culture, and if Damascus architecture is compared it with other Arab regions, the basic unified characteristics are based on one culture and belief, (monotheism).

The most important characteristic is the unity of projection, material, color, shape, symbolism and environmental and climatic conformity. Damascus was subjected to many invasions and occupations for a total period of 2,000 years, these invasions however could not cancel or eliminate the culture and religion of this region and the strength of its civilization and culture constantly overcome the civilization and culture of the invasions and occupations.,

Damascus has preserved its Arab civilization and characteristics throughout the Greek, Roman and Persian eras, or during the domination of foreign rulers, such as Turkish, Circassian, Kurdish or Ottoman rulers. The main ethnics in Damascus are the Arabs, who have three religions:Jewish, Christianity and Islam,in addition to other ethnics settled in Damascus for religious and political reasons.

Error! Reference source not found.shows the distribution of peoples of various backgrounds in Damascus in 1937.

2.1 Kurds

They settled in Damascus since the middle ages in the 12th century, and formed their own communities, like Al Akrad and Sarouja areas. They came as Muslims to participate in the crusade wars and they were very effective in Hittin battle and in liberating Jerusalem. They merged culturally and linguistically, with the Arab culture.

2.2 Circassians

They came from the Caucasian mountains. They are known historically as Mamlouks, and in the modern age, first quarter of the 20th century, many of them migrated from their country during the socialism domination in the previous Soviet Union, because of religious persecution, and like Kurds, they formed their own communities.

2.3 Armenians

Due to the religious persecution, massacres and ethnic elimination to Armenian people by Turkey, large number of them migrated to the Levant and part of them settled in Damascus, especially in Bab Touma area.

2.4 Palestinian Refugees

Large number of them came after the Israeli occupation of Palestine. Most of them Muslims and some Christians, and the majority are Arab in addition to some Circassians, Armenians and Kurds.

2.5 Moroccans

They are Arab and Berbers and all of them are Muslims. Part of them came during the Crusade Wars in the 12th century and the other part after the French occupation to Algeria in 1832. They established several communities in Al Swaiqa and Zuqzq Al Naqeeb.

Turks

They are Muslims, settled in Damascus during the Ottoman occupation in 1516 and they do not have their own communities, although Al Swaiqa area was considered “small Istanbul”.

Minorities and Others

There are ethnic minorities, who came to Damascus individually or as groups from the Islamic world, such as Bosnia, Albania, and Soviet Union countries, Afghanistan, India, Pakistan and Iran

In Addition to these ethnics, there is the internal migration from other governorates to Damascus, especially the Kurds in Syria, who came from Al Hassakeh, Qamishli and Aleppo and settled in Dummar (in Bustan Al Riz) area). It is important to mention that the constitution is civilian, all citizens are equal regardless their ethnics, religion or belief.

Fig (25) Period Distribution of Peoples of Various Backgrounds in Damascus in 1937

5-Historical Areas in the Damascus City

Walled Old City

Damascus was established on four hills, and archaeological excavations proved the urban existence that goes back to the 3rd millennium BC. The urban heritage is almost concentrated in the old city, consisting of historical residential and military constructions such as the Damascus citadel, the wall, towers and a number of unique religious architecture, the most important of which are the Umayyad mosque and the religious schools, such as Al Adliyah, Al Ayyoubiyeh, Al Zahiriyeh and many others, in addition to Khans (Khan Asa`ad Pasha), historical souks (Souk Al Hamidiyah) and many historical houses (Al A`azem,

A`anbar, Al Na`assan. etc.). In addition to its distinguished architecture, it has a distinguished social characteristic, which gave constant life to the city from the day of its establishment until now. The city experience many natural risks (earthquakes, fires and epidemics) and human risks (wars, battles, destruction), yet it kept its unique urban structure, which reflects the close relationship between the Damascenes and their society and environment.

Fig(26) Panoramic View of Damascus

Al Salhiyeh

When the Palestinian refugees came from Jerusalem and other cities, escaping from the Crusades massacres in late 11th century, the Sultan Nour Eddin Zinki ordered to accommodate them at the foot of the Qassyoun mountains, where they settled and established several mosques, and this area was called Al Salhiyeh. This area is very important because it consists of several historical architecture from the Ayyoubid, Mamlouk and Ottoman periods (900 years ago), and the road, which penetrates this area from north to west has historical urban importance, because it includes religious schools, mosques, almshouses, cemeteries and bimaristans (hospitals).

Swaiqet Sarouja

This quarter used to be un-walled small city for the high rank people from

the Mamlouk and Ottoman period. It is penetrated by a main road that branches into small allies, and the area contains important monuments, such as Al Shamiyeh School, Al Ward mosque, Al Jozeh Hammam (bath).

Al Midan Quarter

It was historically known as Al Qubaibat. This area was religiously, economically and commercially important (because of the Hajj caravans) and contains historical monuments from the Mamlouk and Ottoman periods, in addition to several churches.

Qaser Al Hajjaj Quarter and Al Qanawat

They are located at the south-west part out of the wall of the old city, and both of them are located on the path of the Hajj caravan and they have same urban structure of others.

Al Uqaibeh

The name comes from the Aqabeh (obstacle) because of the topographical relieves in the area. It locates at the northern edge of the Barada river. This area goes back to middle ages and expanded around Al Tawbeh mosque.

The common characteristics of the urban structures outside of the wall are that they were established in the middle ages and the unified Arab planning. The protection wall was replaced by the huge gates, which were closed at night during war time. All these structures contain a main large mosque, a main street, souk (marketplace) and narrow streets with dead end allies, in addition to service and commercial facilities, such as khans, hammams, public fountains, religion schools, almshouses and cemeteries.

All house projections are same, but social differences can be noticed by the space of the house, number of sky opening, quality of the material, decoration and wooden finishing and furniture.

The establishment of this type of urban structure was related to the population increase and expansion limitation within the walled city, expanded outside the wall, surrounding the city as a bracelet. The expansion zones were subjected to regular destruction since the early 20th century and constructions laws during the French period encouraged this destruction by using cement (concrete) instead of the traditional materials. Only very lately, it was realized that it would be necessary to protect this unique urban structure, and the historical monuments were registered in the world heritage list. Yet the heritage destruction has still occurred through the illegal constructions and the unscientific restoration processes, and the current laws and regulations are unable to protect these historical areas and zones.

6-Planning for Developing and Preserving Heritage

Impact of Master Plans on Urban Heritage in Damascus:

The first master plan for Damascus was established in 1937, by the French architectures Ecochar and Danjei. They adopted city planning of the beginning of the 20th century (main road network connecting different geometrical shape squares and sub-road network). This style was applied, in the past, to the French cities and known by “the beautiful city movement”. This planning style was a reaction of the narrow serpentine streets and allies existed in that period. The mentioned French architectures applied this planning style not only to Damascus, but to several other Syrian cities.

Fig(27) Distribution of Peoples of Various Backgrounds in Damascus in 1937

Fig(28) Master Plan – Danje 1936

Fig (29) Damascus 1930 – Damascus 1980

DAMAS 1930, 1/20 000. En noir le secteur d'étude

DAMAS 1980, 1/20 000. En noir le secteur d'étude

Fig()

Fig (30) Damascus 1930 – Damascus 1980

Michel Ecochard

PROJET DANGER, 1932
Une voie de « grande circulation » (C1) suit le tracé ouest de l'avenue Malek Fayçal puis oblique vers le boulevard de Bagdad.

PROJET ECOCHARD, 1968
Une voie à circulation rapide passe le long des remparts, le Barada est canalisé.

Fig (31) Master Plane 1968 Ecochard

Some mistakes resulted from that planning, such as the disrespect of the traditional urban structure that prevailed at that time, considering it as disorderly structure that needs radical change. The traditional materials also were disrespected, and the factory cement was established and the use of traditional materials was prohibited in the construction code.

Actually, the problem is not only demolishing the traditional structure and replacing it with modern one, but also, the disrespect of the old city planning considering that there is no plan, but merely narrow twisted allies that need to be replaced by wide streets . Any study of the characteristics and components of the existing planning reveals the result of thousands of years of urban development. It is true that the qualitative changes occurred during the beginning of 20th century (electricity, car, telephone, concrete.etc.) should be considered in the planning process, but yet the characteristics of each city should not be neglected.

At the end of World War II and after independency, Damascus realized that its master plan did not fulfill the needs of development any more so that consequent additions and modifications were made on its master plan. Each area was studied separately and the urgent need for new master plan appeared. Therefore, a contract was made with the architects Ecochar and Banshoya in 1963 to conduct the master plan for Damascus in four years.

Although the new master plan observed the expansion to be in the barren areas, maintaining the green area, and cared about preserving the historical feature of the city, yet the preservation concept was the same as applied nowadays.

Several international conventions on maintaining traditional urban heritage and preserving them as integrated areas, not isolated from the urban surroundings, were issued. These conventions, in addition to the Syrian Archaeological Law, which registers archeological monuments and put them under protection, contribute to giving this heritage its true value.

The committee of studying the Ecochar - Banshoya master plan adopted the list of archaeological monuments provided by the representative of antiquities department in that committee. These monuments were maintained, isolating them from their urban surroundings.

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7- Impact of Ecochar – Banshoya Master Plan on Archaeological Aspects of Damascus

The old city within the wall

Ecochar - Banshoya considered car transport as a very important element that should enter the old city to serve the commercial area and warehouses. The area surrounding the Umayyad mosque was emptied to show the mosque as an important monument within a square as the case of monuments in Europe and the important urban structure was interpenetrated by wide streets. Fortunately, however, this master plan was suspended by a presidential decree and the old city within the wall was registered and a special construction code (No. 826 of 1996) was applied. Subsequently, it was registered in the world heritage list.

Fig (32) Master Plane 1968 Ecochard

Outside the wall

The historical monuments, which are archaeologically registered, were maintained, but, the archaeological area was badly organized, especially in the Sarouja area, where voices became very loud requesting to preserve its remaining distinguished archaeological fabric. Arguments in this concern lasted for many years, and eventually the Supreme Council of Archaeology decided to register the area in addition to other areas in Al Midan and Al Qanawat as shown in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Historical Protected Zones in Damascus

Zone name	Affiliation	No. and date of decision	Organization
Al Midan	Midan	1/145, 1988	Directorate of Antiquities
Al Qanawat	Qanawat Jaddeh	430, 1996	Directorate of Antiquities
Al Midan	Midan Mousilli	1/158, 2004	Ministry of Culture
Qaser Hajjaj - Bab Al Srijah - Tayrouzi Hammam	Bab Al Jabiyeh - Qaber A`atkeh - Birket Hattab -	361, 2006	Ministry of Culture

and mosque	Bab Srijeh - Swaiqa		
Al Qanawat	Qanawat Jaddeh	1/159, 2004	Ministry of Culture
Flous mosque and the neighboring area	Midan	2005	Ministry of Culture
Al Midan	Souk Al Midan	1/157, 2004	Ministry of Culture

The archaeologically monuments registered by a decision of the Minister of Culture are as follows: 271 monuments within the administrative borders of Damascus and 38 sites, 41 tells (hills), and 43 sites under construction in Rural Damascus. There is no urban zone registered in Rural Damascus.

8-Objectives and Recommendations for Heritage Preservation

To include laws and regulation for protecting and developing the ancient urban areas in the planning systems is a new trend. In the UK, for instance, this trend was not adopted till 1969. In the Vines Convention in 1964, the recommendations mentioned “The concept of historical monument does not include the urban construction itself only, but it includes the frame that this monument exists within, and it can not be separated from its function and from the history represented by this monument”. These recommendations were emphasized by the Washington Convention in 1987, which confirmed the protection of the historical characteristic of the city, along with the spiritual and material elements that express this characteristic, especially the relationship between the historical city and its natural or man made environment, and emphasized maintaining the cultural characteristics of the society, no matter how little they are, because they represent the human history. It also mentioned that when the urban or regional master plan of an area includes constructing main streets for cars, these streets should

not penetrate the historical city or the protected urban area, but rather to facilitate accessing to these areas. Actually, the aim of this report is not merely preserving the historical sites in the city, but to confirm adopting the **bases of Arab city planning** during the planning process for the Damascus metropolitan area.

Obviously, there is an essential difference between the modern western planning, which adopts the concept of defining the use of each area, and the Arab planning which adopts the idea of dividing the city into integrated and connected quarters. The Arab city functions as one unit having one center that connects all main streets. This kind of division fulfills human, safety and

practical needs; the socially and economically integrated quarter is the self sufficient cell of the city, in which simple human life concept is realized. Nevertheless, new elements such as car and the modern technical tools and materials of construction should be considered also, although the modern techniques of construction contributed in making the great cities in the world similar in planning and constructing.

In the current planning, car traffic was given the first priority in planning, so the Arab city lost its human characteristic and aspects, and became unable to provide movement facilities for the pedestrians, and houses became distant from each other to leave space for cars, and the ratio of road width and building height differed and accordingly, and shadows that protect pedestrian disappeared. Balance should be realized in order to maintain the identity of the city. This could be realized by defining the role of cars as a service tool, not impinging on social aspect and priority should be given to pedestrian movement. Also, integrated quarters should be established within the urban extension areas, where residents can provide all their needs walking. The western way of planning, which defines residential areas as first degree, second and public one, should be put away, because one of the bases of Arab city is integration between all society classes and economical levels. Commercial centers should be connected to the residential areas, because there is integration between social and commercial life in Arab cities. Probably, one of the reasons why a whole residential streets turn to commercial ones in Damascus, such as Barzeh, Al Yarmouk, Hay Tishreen and others.

The visits to other governorates confirmed the similarity between cities (same buildings, squares etc.), with no distinguishing characteristics. This is applied to Rural Damascus as well, where the traditional urban fabric disappeared and expansions were made on the agricultural lands. Master plans and thoughts are unified. It is a pity that the Directorate of Antiquities does not register residential zones, or at least document them as the Washington Convention recommended by saying “Protection plan should define the buildings that could be dispensable in exceptional circumstances, and prior to making any procedure, **the existing cases in the area should be totally documented.**”

9- Damascus under the list of Unesco 1979

Brief synthesis

Founded in the 3rd millennium B.C., Damascus was an important cultural and commercial centre, by virtue of its geographical position at the crossroads of the orient and the occident, between Africa and Asia. The old city of Damascus is considered to be among the [oldest continually inhabited cities](#) in the world. Excavations at Tell Ramad on the outskirts of the city have demonstrated that Damascus was inhabited as early as 8,000 to 10,000 BC. However, it is not

documented as an important city until the arrival of the [Aramaeans](#). In the Medieval period, it was the centre of a flourishing craft industry, with different areas of the city specializing in particular trades or crafts.

The city exhibits outstanding evidence of the civilizations which created it - Hellenistic, Roman, Byzantine and Islamic. In particular, the Umayyad caliphate created Damascus as its capital, setting the scene for the city's ongoing development as a living Muslim, Arab city, upon which each succeeding dynasty has left and continues to leave its mark.

In spite of Islam's prevailing influence, traces of earlier cultures particularly the Roman and Byzantine continue to be seen in the city. Thus the city today is based on a Roman plan and maintains the aspect and the orientation of the Greek city, in that all its streets are oriented north-south or east-west and is a key example of urban planning.

The earliest visible physical evidence dates to the Roman period - the extensive remains of the Temple of Jupiter, the remains of various gates and an impressive section of the Roman city walls. The city was the capital of the Umayyad Caliphate. However, apart from the incomparable Great Mosque, built on the site of a Roman temple and over-laying a Christian basilica, there is little visible dating from this important era of the city's history. The present city walls, the Citadel, some mosques and tombs survive from the Middle Ages, but the greatest part of the built heritage of the city dates from after the Ottoman conquest of the early 16th century.

Criterion (i): Damascus testifies to the unique aesthetic achievement of the civilizations which created it. The Great Mosque is a masterpiece of Umayyad architecture, which together with other major monuments of different periods such as the Citadel, the Azem Palace, madrasas, khans, public baths and private residences demonstrates this achievement.

Criterion (ii): Damascus, as capital of the Umayyad caliphate - the first Islamic caliphate - was of key importance in the development of subsequent Arab cities. With its Great Mosque at the heart of an urban plan deriving from the Graeco-Roman grid, the city provided the exemplary model for the Arab Muslim world.

Criterion (iii): Historical and archaeological sources testify to origins in the third millennium BC, and Damascus is widely known as among the oldest continually inhabited cities in the world. The incomparable Great Mosque is a rare and extremely significant monument of the Umayyads. The present city walls, the Citadel, some mosques and tombs survive from the Medieval period, and a large part of the built heritage of the city including palaces and private houses dates from after the Ottoman conquest of the early 16th century.

Criterion (iv): The Umayyad Great Mosque, also known as the Grand Mosque of Damascus, is one of the largest mosques in the world, and one of the oldest sites of continuous prayer since the rise of Islam. As such it constitutes an important cultural, social and artistic development.

Criterion (vi): The city is closely linked with important historical events, ideas, traditions, especially from the Islamic period. These have helped to shape the image of the city and impact of Islamic history and culture.

The total Damascus area inside the wall 128 hectare

1-Omayyad Mosque 1.5 hectare

2-Citadel 3.4 hectare

3-Souqe 6.9 hectare

4-Destroyed area 4 hectare

5-Roudes 16.4 hectare

6-fildes 3.1

7-Houses 94.2 hectare

The total Damascus area outside the wall 400 hectare

Fig (33) Damascus Land used – inside the wall

Fig (34) Paver zone for Damascus NO / 582 /A- 2009

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